

An Observational Study on Facebook Feedback, Its Association with Self-Esteem and Its Influence on the Purpose in Life among Medical Students

An Analysis Of Social Media Interaction Patterns And Their Psychological Impact On Medical Students

Vidhya A¹, Sivaraman S², Ronald Roy K³

¹Junior resident, ²HOD and Professor, ³Associate Professor
Psychiatry, Trichy SRM Medical college hospital Research Centre, Tiruchirappalli, India

Abstract

Background: The world's largest online social network, 'Facebook,' has been designed with the "like" option for posted content. Affirmations obtained on virtually posted content correspond positively with self-esteem and subjective well-being. One such important content is profile display photograph likes and reactions. If the Purpose in life is greater, it lessens the sensitivity of self-esteem to Facebook feedback such as likes. This study evaluated the Facebook feedback, its association with self-esteem, and its influence on purpose in life for medical students.

Methods: This was a qualitative cross-sectional study done using heterogeneity sampling, pre-determined inclusion, and exclusion criteria. Data were collected in a preformed and pretested semi-structured proforma, which included socio-demographic profile and the average Facebook user profile. Self-esteem was determined using the Rosenberg self-esteem scale. Purpose in life was determined using the life engagement test. The variables of the questionnaire were analyzed, and statistical analysis of the data was done. Results were represented in textual, tabular, and graphical form. The discussion and conclusion of the study were presented with interpreted results and references.

Results: SPSS 20 was used for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics were reported as frequencies (percentage) for categorical variables. Correlational analysis was done for other variables. The majority of the study participants were between 19 and 25 years of age. The chi-square test was applied, showing that self-esteem had a negative correlation ($p = -0.103$) with expected likes, and purpose in life had no correlation (0.062) with expected likes.

Conclusion: Purpose in life modifies the positive Facebook feedback and its association with self-esteem.

Keywords: Facebook feedback, Rosenberg self-esteem scale, Life engagement test, Purpose in life.

INTRODUCTION

With a single click, users of Facebook, the largest online social network in the world, can "like" the content they are viewing. Liking content has become incredibly popular due to its simplicity, with half of all users liking at least one post each day, and around 4.5 billion likes created daily. However, what effect does this abundance of likes have on the people receiving them? On one hand, mounting evidence suggests a beneficial impact: getting validation for virtual content is positively correlated with subjective well-being and self-esteem and negatively correlated with loneliness. However, relying on approval from others to feel good about oneself could indicate contingent self-worth, which may compromise long-term well-being. Choosing wisely between these options is crucial because a major reason people use Facebook is to gain attention and recognition from others [1].

The **sociometer theory**, which maintains that self-esteem is calibrated to signs of inclusion or rejection within a social context, formed the foundation for this investigation. According to this view, a person's self-perception serves as a dynamic and self-regulating indicator of their relationship value. It has been demonstrated in numerous trials and field investigations that individuals feel more confident when they are (or imagine being) seen as popular, included, or accepted by others. Notably, having more responsive Facebook friends can satisfy psychological needs that go beyond simply having a larger number of friends. Positive feedback, like photo likes, can be viewed as an indication of acceptance in one's social surroundings. Thus, we hypothesized that self-esteem would rise in proportion to the number of likes received on personal photos [2].

It should be noted, however, that there are other factors that may affect how much one's sense of their own relational value influences their self-worth. For example, social inclusion is a far lesser predictor of self-esteem among people driven by strong personal objectives and motives. Therefore, it was hypothesized that the impact of likes on self-esteem would be moderated by a sense of purpose in life, also known as a "self-organizing life aim that organizes and stimulates goals, manages behaviors, and provides a sense of meaning" [3]. This effect should be most pronounced for individuals lacking a clear purpose, but it should not significantly affect those with a strong sense of purpose because they are less dependent on social acceptance for self-worth.

Furthermore, purpose is seen as a prosocial incentive. Individuals with a higher purpose are likely to be less sensitive to encouraging comments on social media, as they work towards achieving objectives that are both personally significant and relevant to the larger world [4]. Their sense of belonging and service to others already serves as their compass. This theory is further supported by research showing that individuals with strong civic and prosocial orientations use Facebook more for informational purposes than for socializing or status enhancement. Emotional effects of Facebook use are greatest for those who feel their life lacks purpose. Therefore, it may be more reliable to disconnect self-esteem from social feedback by appealing to one's sense of personal motivation and prosocial goals [5]. Hence this study aimed to determine Facebook feedback, its association with self-esteem and its influence on purpose in life.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Type of Study: Qualitative Cross-sectional study

Study Setting: Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital Research Centre

Study Population: Medical students

Study Period: August 2021 to February 2022 (6 months)

Sample Size: 100 participants

Ethical Consideration

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee (Ref.No: TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2021-IEC No:009 dated 05.08.2021). Details were collected after obtaining informed consent.

Procedure

Nonprobability sampling (convenient sampling) was used. Medical college students between the ages of 19 and 25 years were included. Students unwilling to participate or not giving consent were excluded. Determination of Facebook feedback was done using the average Facebook user profile. Self-esteem was measured using the Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale, and purpose in life was assessed using the Life Engagement Test.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were reported as frequencies (percentage) for categorical variables. Pearson's correlation was used to find the relationship between positive Facebook feedback, self-esteem, and purpose in life. Data were statistically evaluated using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 26.0., IBM Corp., Chicago, IL.

RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of Expected Likes among Study Participants

Sl. No	Expected Likes	Frequency	Percentage
1	More than 200	34	34%
2	Less than 200	66	66%

Figure 1: Distribution of expected likes among study participants

Table 2: Distribution of Self-esteem among Study Participants

Sl. No	Self-esteem	Frequency	Percentage
1	Normal	86	86%
2	Low	24	24%

Figure 2: Distribution of self-esteem among study participants

Table 3: Distribution of Purpose in Life among Study Participants

Sl. No	Purpose in Life	Frequency	Percentage
1	Clear	82	82%
2	Indecisive	11	11%
3	Unclear	7	7%

Figure 3: Distribution of purpose in life among study participants**Table 4: Correlation of Facebook Feedback (Expected Likes) with Self-esteem and Purpose in Life**

Expected Likes	P value
Normal Self-esteem	-0.103
Clear Purpose in Life	0.062

DISCUSSION

People can share a variety of personal details with large networks of "friends" on social networking sites like Facebook. As online media sharing becomes more and more common, there are still a lot of unanswered concerns about the preconditions for this behaviour. Through contingencies of self-worth, changeable features affecting self-esteem can be approached more nuancedly, and online behaviour may be better understood. People are motivated to create an image of oneself as competent, according to the self-esteem theory of success motivation. This contingency self-worth is an example of a self-preservation aim that is based on competence [6].

Numerous studies have demonstrated the substantial correlation between teenagers' well-being and their sense of self-worth. Most proponents of the theory of self-esteem argue that well-being is the result and self-esteem is the cause.

Drawing from these theoretical frameworks, it is hypothesised that social self-esteem serves as a predictor of well-being, potentially mediating the relationship between using friend networking sites and overall wellbeing [7]. According to two research, not getting many responses from Facebook friends jeopardises one's demands for control, self-worth, belonging, and a purposeful life [8]. Self-esteem is measured using Rosenberg self-esteem scale [9]. According to recent studies, adolescents' reward-processing-related brain areas were more activated when they looked at social media photos that had gotten more likes. If these brain

regions are activated by receiving or witnessing likes, then suppressing responses to them as social validations is probably necessary to reduce reactivity to them. It's interesting to note that having a life goal reduces impulsivity towards reward seeking. Therefore, increased inhibition could be a way via which purpose shapes how social evaluations affect self-esteem. Furthermore, although certain conceptions of purpose characterise it as an inward-looking endeavour, others insist that it necessitates an aim to make a positive impact on the world beyond the self. According to the sociometer viewpoint, purpose can lessen the significance of transient affirmations like likes by reminding people that they are already naturally working towards goals they think have a large societal worth. Purpose in life is assessed using life engagement test [10].

CONCLUSION

Purpose in life modifies the relationship between positive Facebook feedback and self-esteem.

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